

VMG: Requirements for temperature and humidity products for data assimilation

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1) Introduction:

This document aims at reviewing the minimum requirements for data assimilation and long-term reanalysis of temperature and humidity products. This document should help to identify necessary developments needed to foster data assimilation of temperature and humidity products from ground-based remote sensing and UAVs or identify solutions to coordinate a more extensive use of already existing products.

As already reviewed in deliverable 2.1, several ground-based instruments provide complementary information on temperature and humidity in the atmospheric boundary layer (ABL):

- Active sensors provide vertical profiles with a better vertical resolution but cannot provide information within and above clouds due to the attenuation of the lidar signal. They also suffer from a “blind zone” which is in general between the surface and 50 m or as high as a few hundreds of meters. In this document we focus mainly on water vapor lidars (Raman LIDAR (RAM) or DIAL technology)
- Passive instruments do not suffer from any blind zone which makes them sensitive to the very lowest layers of the atmosphere but have a coarser vertical resolution compared to active instruments. Hyperspectral infrared spectrometers (IRS) provide more information on the vertical structure compared to microwave radiometers but their signal is totally attenuated within optically thick clouds similarly to lidars. Microwave radiometers (MWR) have the possibility to provide vertical profiles in all-sky conditions well resolved for temperature in the boundary layer but with a poor description of the vertical structure for water vapor.

In addition to ground-based remote-sensing instruments, UAVs now offer new possibilities for automatic and high temporal frequency sounding in the ABL.

Depending on the chosen approach either level2 products (retrieved temperature and humidity from ground-based instrument) or level1 raw data (brightness temperatures for passive instruments, lidar backscattered power or temperature and humidity measurements for UAVs) can be directly assimilated into numerical weather prediction (NWP) models.

2) List of already existing data assimilation or long-term reanalysis studies classified by instrument

This section aims at providing a synthesis of already existing data assimilation or long-term reanalysis experiments where level1 or level2 data from MWR, IRS, UAVs or water vapor lidars have been assimilated.

Abbreviations:

EnKF: Ensemble Kalman Filter

LETKF: Local Ensemble Transform Kalman Filter

3D-Var: Three-Dimensional Variational Assimilation

QPF: Quantitative Precipitation Forecast

FSS: Fraction Skill Score

DWL: Doppler Wind Lidar

OSSE: Observing System Simulation Experiments

DA: Data Assimilation

References	Instrument	Product	Quick synthesis
Otkin 2011 Hartung 2011 <i>DOI:</i> <i>10.1175/2011MWR3622.1</i> <i>DOI:</i> <i>10.1175/2011MWR3623.1</i>	DWL MWR AERI RAM	Temperature Profiles Humidity Profiles Wind profiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - OSSE (simulated data) - 140 profile stations in the USA - ENKF - DA for 1 day in winter - Largest impact on analysis and short-term forecasts when wind included with T/Q
Caumont 2016 <i>DOI:10.1002/qj.2860</i>	MWR	Temperature Profile Humidity Profile	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Real data - 13 MWR stations - AROME 3D-VAR every hour - 41 days - Small impact except for QPF for larger rainfall accumulations.
He 2020 <i>DOI:</i> <i>10.1080/16742834.2019.1709299</i>	MWR	Temperature and Humidity Profile	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Real data - 2 stations - 4 days assimilation - WRF DA every 6 hours - Improved distribution and localisation of precipitation
Thomas et al 2024 (in review, QJRMS)	MWR	Temperature profile	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Real data - 6 stations - AROME 3DVAR every hour - 3 months experience in

			<p>winter</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improvement in the temperature bias up to 6 hour forecasts - Improvement of fog scores based on surface visibility
<p>Leuenberger 2020, <i>DOI:</i> <i>10.1175/BAMS-D-19-0119.1</i></p>	<p>Raman Lidar UAVS</p>	<p>Temperature and humidity profiles</p>	<p><u>Raman Lidar:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - LETKF - 1 day experiment - Convective system associated with a cold front - Improved forecasts of precipitation up to 24 hours <p><u>UAVs:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Winter fog (6 cases) - LETKF - 3 UAVs profiles up to 1800m - Simulation of a much larger fog area with UAVs assimilated at 00 UTC compared to satellite images. - Neutral impact when strong synoptic-scale forcing
<p>Qi et al 2022 <i>DOI:</i> <i>10.3390/atmos13010074</i></p>	<p>MWR</p>	<p>Temperature Profile Humidity Profile</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - RMAP-ST assimilation system - WRF 3DVAR - 5 real stations - 1 day experiment: heavy precipitation case - Improved representation of precipitation and heat urban island before rain.
<p>J. Vural C. Merker A. Schomburg <i>DOI:</i> 10.1002/qj.4634</p>	<p>MWR</p>	<p>Brightness temperatures</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Direct assimilation - LETKF - Two different setups: MeteoSwiss presents the operational assimilation of two stations, Deutscher Wetterdienst presents

			<p>experiments focusing on selection of channels and vertical localisation with one station only</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Positive impact on model analyses: the impact on the brightness temperature is positive, so the match of brightness temperature between model and observations is improved after assimilation. - Neutral impact on forecasts: the impact on model prognostic variables is more difficult to achieve, results are still not fully satisfying, more work is needed on the assimilation side.
<p>Hu et al 2019, DOI: 10.1175/WAF-D-18-0200.1</p>	<p>AERI DWL</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Temperature and humidity profiles from AERI - Horizontal Wind from the Doppler Wind Lidar 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Single case study of tornado in USA great plains. - WRF model at 3km resolution. - Inflation technique of the ENKF. - Six sites with AERI and DWL - Depending on the inflation technique used in the DA system, the convective initiation can be forecast with the assimilation of AERI and DWL observations - More impact from the assimilation of the AERI moisture field compared to wind observations - Largest impact when both AERI and DWL assimilated together
<p>Degelia et al 2020 DOI: 10.1175/MWR-D-20-0118.1</p>	<p>AERI DWL</p>	<p>Temperature and humidity profiles from AERI</p> <p>Horizontal Wind from DWL</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Six stations over the US Great Plains - 13 case studies of nocturnal convective initiation (CI). - GSI-based EnKF system.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Small but consistent improvement with all verification metrics with the assimilation of thermodynamic profilers. - Degradation often observed when assimilating wind observations probably due to the under-estimation of wind profiler observation errors.
Lewis et al, 2020: DOI:10.3390/atmos11070729	AERI	Temperature and humidity profiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - One case study of severe convective weather event - WRF EnKF - One station - Improved FSS scores in the first hours of forecast with the assimilation of AERI data.
C. Augros / P. Brousseau (Météo-France) on going	Raman lidars	Humidity Profiles (Specific Humidity)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - monitoring and assimilation experiments for 5 water vapor lidars (French and Spanish Mediterranean coasts) => assimilated variable = specific humidity - AROME 3D-EnVar - Autumn 2022

Table 1. Synthesis of published papers where level1 or level2 data from MWR, IRS, UAVs or water vapor lidars have been assimilated.

Additional references:

Coniglio et al 2019, DOI: 10.1175/MWR-D-18-0351.1

Degelia et al 2019, DOI: 10.1175/MWR-D-18-0423.1

3) Main Requirements in terms of data format / precision and temporal frequency

In this section, the main requirements in terms of data format / precision and temporal frequency are listed from the WMO OSCAR requirements. Only requirements for high resolution and nowcastings models are listed as this is where we can expect the largest impact from ground-based remote sensing network.

Additional requirements were included based on the actual needs expressed by data assimilation experts: one for temperature and two for brightness temperature (for direct assimilation purposes).

NWS refers to National Weather Services.

Variable	Data format	Precision	Observing cycle	Vertical Resolution	Timeliness
Temperature High Resolution NWP	BUFR	G: 0.5 K	G: 15 min.	G: 100 m	G: 10 min.
		B: 1 K	B: 60 min.	B: 250 m	B: 30 min.
Temperature Profile Intermediate Needs for NWS	BUFR	0.8 K	30 min.	< 500m	20'
Temperature Nowcasting	BUFR	G: 0.5 K	G: 5 min.	G: 100m	G: 5 min.
		B: 1 K	B: 10 min.	B: 300m	B: 10 min.
Specific Humidity High resolution NWP	BUFR	G: 2%	G: 15 min	G: 100 m	G: 15 min
		B: 5%	B: 60 min	B: 200 m	B: 30 min
Specific Humidity Nowcasting	BUFR	G: 2%	G: 5 min	G: 100 m	G: 5 min
		B: 5%	B: 10 min	B: 300 m	B: 10 min
Brightness temperatures Humidity Channels	BUFR	1 K	30 min.	/	20 min.
Brightness Temperatures Temperature Channels	BUFR	0.5 K	30 min.	/	20 min.

Table 2. Lines colored in light pink show the list of WMO OSCAR requirements for the atmospheric boundary layer and high-resolution/nowcasting NWP application areas. Only two requirement levels are reported here for each parameter: goal (G) and breakthrough (B). From: <https://space.oscar.wmo.int/variables>. An intermediate need for temperature has been included based on PROBE members expertise in data assimilation as well as requirements needed for brightness temperatures.

For data assimilation in NWS it appears that the most important requirements are the precision, the observation cycle and timeliness. The precision should be better than the actual NWP background errors in order to positively impact the analyses and forecasts. The observation cycle and timeliness should be short enough in order to receive the observations in time to be assimilated in each assimilation cycle (at least one per hour).

4) Specific requirements and tools related to data assimilation systems

Current operational data assimilation systems rely on several assumptions that must be satisfied in order to correctly assimilate new observations to obtain a positive impact on weather forecasts. When raw level1 measurements are directly assimilated instead of derived products, fast observation operators are also needed to translate model variables into the observation space. This section aims at summarizing the main requirements and/or tools that are already available or need to be developed to foster data assimilation of ground-based remote sensing observations related to temperature and humidity.

- **Channel or vertical level selection:** Variational data assimilation system or Ensemble Kalman Filters make use of an observation error covariance matrix which is often considered as diagonal. In such cases, observation errors (either brightness temperatures (BT) for level1 data or derived temperature and humidity profiles for level2 data) must be uncorrelated. For passive instruments (MWR / IRS), some correlations might exist between BT measured at the same channel but at different elevation angles. The same appears in derived temperature and humidity profiles where the vertical grid of the product is often higher than the true resolution of the retrieval. To facilitate data assimilation, it is important to provide information about observation error correlations to help national weather services in the selection of the passive channels or vertical levels that can be truly considered as un-correlated.

Several methods already exist to provide this information, among them we can cite:

- **DFS method** (based on the Degrees of Freedom of the Signal): with this method, only vertical levels that are a full DFS apart are selected for data assimilation (Turner and Löhnert 2021, DOI: 10.5194/amt-14-3033-2021). This method is only possible when vertical profiles are derived with optimal estimation approaches (that can also be called one dimensional variational methods).
- **Inter-level error covariance method:** in this method the true vertical resolution is directly inferred from differences between the retrieved profiles and considered truth profiles from reference measurements like

radio-sounding observations (Liljegren et al 2005, DOI: 10.1109/TGRS.2004.839593) => several databases of co-located MWR and RS profiles exist to calculate this covariance but there is no public dissemination of the results to end-users.

It is important to note that main NWP centers have recently been working at the integration of non-diagonal observation error covariance matrices in their systems. This is for example the case at ECMWF for some microwave radiometers and for hyperspectral infrared sounders. In that case, it is important to provide assimilation teams with an estimation of observation error covariances. If a full matrix can be used within the assimilation system, this step of observation thinning (either in brightness temperature space or retrieved profile space) can be avoided.

- **Specification of observation errors:** For all data assimilation systems, observation errors covering instrumental error, forward operator and representation error must be specified. Degelia et al 2020 demonstrated clearly that an erroneous specification of observation errors can lead to a degradation of the forecast skills when assimilating new observations in current NWP models. A good specification of observation errors is thus essential to pave the way for an improvement of NWP forecasts through the assimilation of new observations. For the specification of instrumental errors, brightness temperature and radiance errors can be provided by manufacturers (derived after calibration). For MWR, the RPG manufacturer now includes the delivery of the observation error covariance matrix within the manufacturer software. For IRS radiance observations, the spectral random error is also a direct output of the calibration routine (Revercomb et al. Applied Optics 1988). When retrieved profiles are assimilated, the expected uncertainty is provided by optimal estimation approaches for each profile to users. In the case of multi-variate regressions or neural networks, an estimation of the expected errors can be provided through the use of the test database (sample of profiles not used during the training of the coefficients but used to evaluate the expected accuracy of the retrieved profiles). However, these errors are often under-estimated compared to the true uncertainty. In fact, they generally use simulated measurements within the training. Simulated measurements are then perturbed according to the expected instrumental errors. However, each instrument has its own instrumental errors and the profile uncertainty also depends on the instrumental weighting functions, whose position depends on the atmospheric conditions. One challenge for the assimilation of future ground-based networks will be that observation errors are in general instrument dependent (even for the same type of instrument).

For forward operator errors, Cimini et al 2018 (DOI: 10.5194/acp-18-15231-2018) propose an approach to estimate the absorption model uncertainty due to uncertainty in the spectroscopic parameters. The approach has been applied to microwave frequencies (20-60 GHz) and provides now references for forward model uncertainties. For IRS radiance observations, a fast forward model still needs to be developed for a direct assimilation of radiance observations.

Representativeness errors have also to be specified and are still an un-resolved issue. In fact, the footprint of the remote sensor is usually much smaller than the

horizontal resolution of the model. Thus, the observation could see a cloud that is smaller than the horizontal spacing of the model. Thus, if we assimilate the BT or radiances, then the model must be able to build subgrid scale clouds. Due to the difference between the observation footprint and model resolution, poorer performance can also be observed near coastlines or complex terrain compared to the assimilation over flat and land-locked terrain.

As assimilation algorithms do not need to separate the sources of errors (instrumental errors, forward model errors, representativeness errors), diagnostics like the Desroziers (Desroziers et al 2005, DOI: /10.1256/qj.05.108) algorithm can be useful to tune these errors (this diagnostics can be used after a first assimilation experiment run with a first approximation of observation errors and estimates the total full observation error covariance matrix).

- **Bias correction**: the bias correction of observations is an important step before data assimilation whatever the assimilation system as data assimilation algorithms assume un-biased observations. NWS prefer to use their own bias correction scheme (sometimes adaptive) as the bias correction also depends on the chosen observation operator. However, providing information on a first estimation of the instrument biases appears to be relevant for the assimilation teams. The observation minus background monitoring developed by Météo-France and using the fast radiative transfer model RTTOV-gb appears to be well suited for an implementation at the European scale (through E-Profile and ACTRIS infrastructure). This tool based on De Angelis et al 2017 (DOI: 10.5194/amt-10-3947-2017) has already been used for several instruments at different locations in France and Europe (Cologne, Lindenberg, SOFOG3D and PANAME experiments). This methodology needs to be tested for IRS.

The methodology needs to be tested for the assimilation of retrieved profiles too.

- **Forward operators**: When assimilating brightness temperatures (BT) or radiances, forward operators are needed to convert the model variables into equivalent BT. The adjoint of the tangent linear is also necessary for a fast computation of Jacobians (derivatives of the BT with respect to model control variables). For MWR measurements, the fast RTTOV-gb model was developed (De Angelis 2016, DOI: 10.5194/gmd-9-2721-2016). Additional validation is probably necessary for low elevation angles as RTTOV-gb was derived from the satellite version of RTTOV which is not optimized for low elevation angles. For IRS radiance observations, a fast forward model still needs to be developed for a direct assimilation of radiance observations.
- **Time averaging**: observations from remote sensors are generally available at a high temporal resolution (like 1 sec.). Information about the most relevant time averaging could help the users when assimilating the data.
- **Localization**: For the LETKF, the brightness temperature data needs to be assigned to a specific height. The observation can also be assimilated without localizing the information in height allowing the observation to impact the whole model profile. This tends to lead to a slight change in temperature and humidity profiles smeared out

over the whole height. When a sharper localisation is used, a localized substantial impact in one height region can be observed with potentially beneficial impact.

Additionally, a localisation range needs to be specified to indicate in which height range around the location of the measurement it should be considered for the analysis. For the height assignment and the localisation range, the most important information is the height region from which the information in the brightness temperature comes from. More detailed information could be very helpful here for data assimilation team to increase the benefit of new observations. One approach is to use the Jacobians provided by fast forward models like RTTOV-gb for example.

- **Background-error-covariance-matrix:** For current data assimilation systems, the accuracy of the analysis and the benefit of remote sensing observations depends on the specification of the background-error-covariance matrix **B**. This matrix specifies how much weight is given to the a priori profile compared to the observation, specifies how the information from the localized observation is spread in the model space both vertically and horizontally (for 3D/4D-Var assimilation), and imposes the balance between the model control variables. It is now well known that background covariances highly depend on the atmospheric conditions. In fact, fog or convective conditions will exhibit different behaviors compared to clear-sky conditions in terms of vertical correlations and variable cross-correlations (Martinet et al 2020, DOI: 10.5194/amt-13-6593-2020, Marquet et al 2022, DOI:10.5194/amt-15-2021-2022). A good prescription of vertical correlations dependent on the atmospheric boundary layer height is also crucial to avoid the spread of punctual observations over a large region where atmospheric variables are no longer coupled. For variational data assimilation, the use of ensemble data assimilation to derive a spatially and weather-dependent **B** matrix that mimics in a variational context the approach taken in the stochastic ensemble Kalman filter should help a more appropriate assimilation of ground-based remote sensing instruments. As demonstrated in Hu et al 2019 (DOI: 10.1175/WAF-D-18-0200.1), the impact of the assimilation of IRS and DWL observations assimilated through an EnKF algorithm depends on the inflation technique used to take into account the ensemble under-dispersion. For variational assimilation schemes, similar issues can appear due to the under-dispersion of ensemble members used to derive the flow-dependent **B** matrix especially within the atmospheric boundary layer. A good representation of the **B** matrix is a key challenge for observations sensitive to the boundary layer transition and evolution.